

LCA/LCC survey for WP1 “Protein crop production”
Version 1.0, 2020-08-06

S. No.	Data required	Unit	Value	Remarks (additional information, data source, uncertainties, etc.)
General				
1	In which country is your farm located?			
2	How much is the cropped area of the farm?	Hectare		
3	Do you own the land that you farm?	Yes/No		
4	Do you lease the land that you farm?	Yes/No		
5	What is the value of cropped area?	€/hectare		
6	How many horsepower (hp) do you have at farm (sum of all tractor power)?	HP		
7	Are there any certifications or Eco-labels you use with your farm product? If Yes, please specify the name.	Yes/No		
8	Is there any cost involved in certifications or Eco-labeling of your farm product? If Yes, then how much?	Yes/No €/annum		
9	If the products are processed on-farm, are you HACCP certified (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point/Plan)?	Yes/No		
10	How would you define your growing practices? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organically certified • Organic practice but not certified • Conventional • Other If other, please specify:	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		Other can be Minimum tillage/No tillage, conservation agriculture practices
11	What is the percent area of most important crops in the last year?	Percent or Months		e.g., 20% winter cereals, 30% legumes etc.

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12	What is the textural class of the soil? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loam • Sandy-loam • Silt-loam • Clay-loam • Silt • Clay • Sand 	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		This is the classification of soil textural classes as defined by the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA).
13	Are there any farming-specific taxes? If yes, then which taxes do you pay?	Yes/No		
14	Are there any farming-specific subsidies? If yes, which subsidies do you receive?	Yes/No		
Crop specific on-farm activities (fill this section for each of the following crops)				
15	Which crop is grown?	<input type="checkbox"/> Fava beans <input type="checkbox"/> Lentils <input type="checkbox"/> Chickpeas <input type="checkbox"/> Quinoa		
16	From how many years are you growing this crop?	Years		
17	Area used for this crop last year?	Hectare		
18	What was the previous crop?	Name of crop		
19	What was the harvesting time of previous crop?	Month		
20	What was the plan for management of residues from previous crop?	<input type="checkbox"/> Shredding residues <input type="checkbox"/> Shredding residues and burying <input type="checkbox"/> Left on the soil <input type="checkbox"/> Residues removed for livestock <input type="checkbox"/> Removed Bedding <input type="checkbox"/> Residues sold in the market		

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		<input type="checkbox"/> Residues burned			
21	How much labour was required for the management of previous crop residues?	Hours/hectare			
22	How much energy/fuel was required for the management of previous crop residues?	Litres/hectare			
23	If you used Cover Crops, What was the time of sowing of cover crop?	Month			
24	What was the species used as cover crop?	<input type="checkbox"/> Legume <input type="checkbox"/> Cereal <input type="checkbox"/> Brassica <input type="checkbox"/> Others or Mix of above			
25	How many seeds were required for cover crop?	Kg/hectare			
26	What was the cost of the seeds of cover crop?	€/kg			
27	How much was the cost of sowing the cover crop?	€/hectare			
28	How much was the cost of terminating the cover crop?	€/hectare			
29	How much labour was required for the cover crop?	Hours/hectare			
30	How much energy/fuel was required for the cover crop?	Litres/hectare			
31	Information regarding primary tillage and sowing operations of concerned crop :	No. of operations	Energy/fuel required (l/ha)	Labour (hour/ha)	Total cost (machinery and labour) (€/ha)
	• Chisel plough				
	• Disc harrow				
	• Grain drill				
	• Grain drill – no tillage				
	• Moldboard plough				
	• Roller harrow				

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roller packer Rotary hoe / bed tiller Row crop cultivator Row crop planter Subsoiler Tine harrow / seed handling transport Tooth harrow Specify Other..... 				
32	How many seeds are required?	Kg/hectare			
33	What is the cost of the seeds?	€/kg			
34	What is the type of fertilizer used? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic Chemical-based Both 	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		Please also indicate the NPK value/composition of the fertilizer	
35	How much quantity of fertilizer is needed per kg of yield?	N (kg/ha)	P or P ₂ O ₅ (kg/ha)	K or K ₂ O (kg/ha)	Total mass (kg/ha)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic Mineral Others (eg Organo-Mineral)..... 				
36	What is the cost of fertilizer?	€/ha			
37	How much energy/fuel is consumed in fertilizing?	l/ha			
38	How much irrigation water is required?	millimeter		10 m ³ /ha = 1 mm of water	
39	What is the source of water for irrigation?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Groundwater Surface water 				
40	Type of irrigation system:	Man time (h/ha/irrigation)		Duration of irrigation (h/ha/irrigation)	

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sprinkler • Ranger/pivot • Furrow • Dripline • Other 					
41	Total energy (electricity/fuel) is consumed by the irrigation system (pumps)?	kWh/ha or l/ha				
42	How much fuel is needed for the harvesting of the crop?	Litre/hectare				
43	How much are the harvest and post-harvest losses?	%				% or mass related. Losses during drying, cleaning of seeds, etc.
44	Is there any application of lime before sowing? If yes, please mention the quantity.	Yes/No Kg/hectare				
45	What is the price of lime?	€/Kg				
46	Information about weeding –	Man hour (h)	No. of intervention	Type of ingredient/machinery	Q.ty (Kg/Ha)	Cost of ingredient (€/Ha)
	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemical					
	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical					
	<input type="checkbox"/> Manual					
	<input type="checkbox"/> Combination					
47	Do you use pesticides to protect the crop against pathogens, pests, and other insects? If yes, what?	Yes/No				To protect the crop against weeds, pests, diseases, etc.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insecticides • Fungicides • Seed protection • Slugs 	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>				

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Others 	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	How much for each?	Kg/ha		
48	What is the price of these agents? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insecticides Pesticides Fungicides others 	€/kg		
Post-harvesting activities				
49	How much is the average fresh yield?	Kg/ha		
50	How much is the average dry yield?	Kg/ha		
51	How much is the farm gate price of the yield?	€/t		
52	Where do you sell your yield? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wholesale Retail Farmers cooperative Government Others If others, please specify:	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>		
53	What kind of on-farm post-harvesting activities are done? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drying & cleaning Grinding Others If others, please specify:	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	Cost (€/t)	Energy (KWh/t)
54	How far is the processing facility for off-farm activities?	Kilometer		

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55	Do you have any need for storage premises? If yes, how much area is required for the storage facility?	Yes/No m ³		
56	How much energy is required to maintain a storage facility (e.g., air conditioning, lighting?)	kWh/year		
57	How much is the cost to maintain a warehouse (excluding the energy cost)?	€/month		
58	What is the storage moisture content of the crop?	%		
59	What is the nutrient content of the crop? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nitrogen (N) • Protein 			
60	What is the transportation distance of waste from the farm?	Km		
61	Which kind of crop residues are generated and how much is produced and how is it treated/used afterward?			Treatment method and/or application
	<input type="checkbox"/> Shredding residues			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Shredding residues and burying			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Left on the soil			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Residues removed for livestock			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Bedding			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Residues sold in the market <input type="checkbox"/> Residues burned			
62	Is there any product against which you compare your farm product? If yes, please specify:	Yes/No		

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Additional information about machinery, equipment and administration				
63	How much lubricant is used in the entire process of farming?	Liters		
64	What is the average cost of the lubricant?	€/liter		
65	What is the initial investment cost of machinery and equipment used for farming (e.g. plowing, sowing, watering, harvesting, etc.)?	€/year		
66	What is the depreciation cost of machinery and equipment used for farming annually?	€/year		
67	Is there any insurance for machinery and equipment used for farming? If yes, please mention the cost of insurance.	Yes/No		
68	What are the costs involved in the maintenance and repairs of farming machinery and equipment?	€/year		
69	How many hours of farm labor are needed in 1 year?	€/year		
70	What is the total cost of labor employed for farming (yourself included)?	€/year		
71	Do you pay any interest on advance capital and capital goods? If yes, then how much?	Yes/No		
		€ / year		
72	How much is the miscellaneous cost (e.g. expert consultation, soil survey, crop quality testing, etc.)?	€/year		